

Mapping textures of polar ice cores using 3D laboratory X-ray microscopy

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Radiographs of ice before and after data acquisition

Figure S1. Examples of X-ray projections. At the top, raw X-ray diffraction patterns demonstrate how the source-beam aperture affects the shapes of diffraction spots when using the beam geometry and flat panel detector as described in the **Methods**. The green checkmarks indicate what aperture and exposure time proved optimal for DCT data acquisition on samples with different amounts of deformation. Binarized images to the right show how deformed grains are defined using a magnified area of a diffraction projection from the NEEEM sample. The elongated diffraction spot associated with cloudy areas of intensity represents diffraction primarily from a large, distorted grain with orientation spread, and the linear upper and lower boundaries of the most intense area reflect confinement of the source-beam to the pinhole aperture. The pink transparent region represents the segmentation of diffraction spot(s), and the numerous green lines represent the forward-projected outlines of a single $\{hkl\}$ (lattice plane) family (one of several used for indexing grains; Bachmann and others, 2019). When grains are defined during reconstruction, the average forward projection shown represents the average grain orientation. Below, the radiographs of the NEEEM sample show its appearance before and after a 24-hour-long period of ACT-DCT data acquisition. The only notable difference in the “after” image is the presence of a frost layer on the upper surface of the sample. The uppermost temperature sensor and its copper wires are in the field of view. The wires had negligible effects on diffraction projections.

Figure S2. Comparing grain size information between 3D grain maps and simulated 2D slices of the Eurocore deep ice sample. **(a)** The 3D grain map, colored by grain diameter, was sliced orthogonally. X and Z slices simulate the typical vertical (X) and horizontal (Z) cuts made of ice cores. **(b-c)** Multiple XYZ slices in these plots represent 60 μm intervals (i.e., the reconstructed voxel size of DCT data). Grain sizes calculated from 3D volumetric data are plotted against grain sizes calculated from combined XYZ orthogonal slices, hence the 1:1 line, as well as the average 2D size of each grain found across XYZ slices combined. Each grain's average size based on either all X-slices or all Z-slices is also compared to its volume-calculated size, with the full 2D size range for each grain plotted as vertical bars. Note that **(b)** plots diameters represent equivalent sphere (3D) or circle (2D) diameters, whereas **(c)** plots the major-axis length of grains based on ellipsoid (3D) and ellipse (2D) fitting.

Eurocore and NEEM samples: 2D grain size distributions for the X-slice and Z-slice

Figure S3. Grain size distributions for the single X-slice and Z-slice of the Eurocore and NEEM samples in **Figure 5** of the main text and **Figure S2**.

Figure S4. Comparing pole figure analyses of firn grain orientations based upon count, volume, and grain size fraction. Pole figures provide views down the sample Z-axis, parallel to the ice-core axis. Analytical details are provided in the **Methods**. Note that glaciological studies employing EBSD of ice may instead represent the *a*-axes as $[11\bar{2}0]$ ($-a_3$), which is symmetrically equivalent to $[2\bar{1}\bar{1}0]$ ($+a_1$) (e.g., see Qi and others, 2019).

Firn and NEEM samples: Grain misorientation statistics

Figure S5. Grain-misorientation plots supporting observations reported for the EGRIP firn and NEEM deep ice samples in Sections 3.4 and 3.5.

Figure S6. Additional analytical plots supporting observations reported in Section 3.5. The Flinn diagram for bubbles in the Eurocore sample represents an inset of the diagram included in **Figure 10** of the main text. The lower plot shows the distribution of the bubbles based on bubble volume and ellipsoid factor.

Bubbles in Eurocore deep ice: Stacked distribution of intragranular bubble-axis directions

Figure S7. Stacked histograms showing the distribution of angle-differences between directions of bubble axes and the host-grain c-axis, with respect to how the host-grain c-axis is oriented relative to the compression axis (Z). The “grain groups” represent grains within 10-degree radial intervals away from the vertical (Z) direction, which represents the ice-core axis and direction of maximum compression. In the legend, the average c-axis angle misorientation from the Z-direction is reported for each “grain group”.

REFERENCES

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- Qi C and 8 others** (2019) Crystallographic preferred orientations of ice deformed in direct-shear experiments at low temperatures. *The Cryosphere* **13**(1), 351–371. doi: [10.5194/TC-13-351-2019](https://doi.org/10.5194/TC-13-351-2019)